

Dynamics Simulation Approach in Analyzing Pension Expenditure

Hasimah Sapiri, Anton Abdulbasah Kamil, Razman Mat Tahar and Hanafi Tumin

Abstract—Salary risk and demographic risk have been identified as main risks in analyzing pension expenditure particularly in Defined Benefit pension plan. Therefore, public pension plan in Malaysia is studied to analyze pension expenditure due to salary and demographic risk. Through the literature review and interview session with several officers in public sector, factors affecting pension expenditure are determined. Then, the inter-relationships between these factors are analyzed through causal loop diagram. The System Dynamics model is later developed using iThink software to show how demographic and salary changes affect the pension expenditure. Then, by using actual data, the impact of different policy scenarios on pension expenditure is analyzed. It is shown that dynamics simulation model of pension expenditure is useful to evaluate the impact of changes and policy decisions on risk particularly involving demographic and salary risk.

Keywords—Demographic and Salary risk, Pension Expenditure, Public Policy, System Dynamics.

I. INTRODUCTION

PENSION is a fixed income received by a worker after retirement. Pension is usually a stream payment made in form of annuity to a retired employee. There is also retirement plan where the benefits in form of accumulations can be withdrawn in lump-sum upon retirement. Generally, there are two types of pension plans; Defined Benefit (DB) plan and Defined Contribution (DC) plan. Defined Benefit plan is a pension plan where the retirement benefit is calculated based on last salary, years of employment, retirement age and other factors. Usually in this pension plan, the benefit is paid in form of annuity. Meanwhile, Defined Contribution plan is a retirement plan where each worker possesses own individual account and the retirement benefit is based on employer's contribution and investment return. Generally,

A worker in this plan can withdraw their retirement benefit in form of lump-sum of cash.

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Due to demographic changes and increasing pension spending, pension systems around the world are in flux conditions [1]. This condition is caused by uncertainties or inherent risk that affects the pension scheme. The existence of risk will also affect the pension expenditure. Among the risk that the sponsor of pension plan particularly in DB plan is exposed to, are demographic risk and salary risk [2]. Demographic risk is defined as the increasing risk due to population aging while salary risk refers to the salary growth affecting the cost of providing pension benefits [2]. The increasing exposure to risk introduces the world of pension risk management that all sponsors have to realize and investigate properly. Therefore, do the sponsor of pension plan is aware on the exposure of increasing risk involved? Most importantly, how will the risk influence the pension plan? The complex phenomenon of demographic and salary changes in a pension plan involves numerous factors which are interconnected in a different directions. Hence, this study attempts to develop a policy design model which analyzes pension expenditure as a result of demographic risk and salary risk.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

System Dynamics (SD) technique exists in early 1960s when Jay W. Forrester of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology invented the methodology to study a non-linear system and feedback control in engineering sciences. With the aid of computer simulation, it is a powerful tool that can be used in understanding complex system. System Dynamics originally based on feedback control theory which includes both hard (quantitative) and soft (qualitative) approaches in analyzing the dynamic behaviors of the development and changes of a system [3]. The strength of SD is it can help to improve decision making process and policy formation, through its' characteristics of incorporate all the relevant cause and effect relationships and feedback loops in a dynamic behavior modes of systems. By developing mathematical model using differential equation concept and in virtue of computer simulation technology, SD is capable in solving a dynamic, varied, interdependent and complex system such as the problem of investigating the impact of demographic and salary risk on pension expenditure.

As proposed by [3], there are three general steps in developing system dynamics model as shown in fig. 1. These steps will be used in order to analyze pension expenditure due to demographic and salary risk. The step started with problem description which involves the process of understanding the problem, system characteristics is deepened, also factors that

affected pension expenditure and system boundaries is recognized. Then, development of dynamic hypothesis consists of building a causal loop diagram shows the causality between the factors that had been recognized. Lastly, the process ended with developing a system dynamic model through computer simulation.

Fig. 1 The process of system dynamics model development

III. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

In this research, Malaysia public pension plan is studied to analyze pension expenditure due to salary and demographic risk. In Malaysia, public pension plan is also exposed to demographic risk and salary risk since the public pension plan is based on unfunded Defined Benefit (DB) plan. In this pension plan, the employees' benefits after retirement are determined by their final basic salary and duration of services which is the maximum duration of services is 25 years (300 months). Also, the retirement benefits are paid through government budget. This pension plan is available for permanent public workers who have met certain requirements and being confirmed in the service. After confirmation, the public employees get to choose their desired pension plan between two plans offered. If the worker chooses DB plan, he/she has to be in service not less than 10 years in order to be eligible to receive 2% of pension benefit from his/her last basic salary for every accumulated services. Workers who have worked for at least 25 years and above are eligible to receive 50% pension annuity from their last basic salary. The pension annuity will be paid until the worker pass away and the annuity is continuously paid to the eligible family members. The pension benefit received by eligible family member is known as derivative pension. The compulsory retirement age in this pension plan is 55 years old, but the retirement age has been raised up to 56 years old in October, 2001 and then to 58 years old effective on July, 2008. However, the increment of retirement age does not indicate that the maximum duration of service will also change. The maximum duration of service can also be amended without increasing the retirement age. Therefore, the percentage of pension annuity is depended on the amendment of maximum duration of service. Hence, effective July, 2008, public workers who have been in service for 30 years and above are eligible to receive 60% pension annuity from their last basic salary.

There are three groups of employees in Malaysia's public sector which are top management group, management & professional group and supporting group (supporting group is divided to supporting I and supporting II group). Each group is classified by salary schemes also known as scheme of service; which indicate the priority in establishment and level of salary. In Malaysia's

public sector, there are two types of salary changes involved; the salary increased due to yearly salary increment and salary adjustment. Yearly salary increment is an even salary increment for all workers which ranges between 3% - 9% from their basic salary while salary adjustment is defined as an adjustment in a worker's basic salary announced by the policy makers every 5 years period depended on the government's financial capability or when there is a need in doing so, such as due to increasing living cost and etc. Between years of 1995 until 2008, the public workers had received 4 salary adjustments which are in 2000, 2002, 2003 and the latest in 2007 (table I). The salary adjustment rate in 2000 and 2002 is a 10% increment from basic salary for all groups of service. In 2003, salaries have been adjusted not according to the percentage. The salary increment is in amount of RM110 (for top management group), RM65 (for management & professional group) and RM15 (for supporting group). Then, most recently in 2007, the salary adjustment is made by group of service as shown in the table I. Workers in top management group received an increment of 7.5% from their basic salary while workers in management & professional group and supporting group received an increment of 15% and 25%-35% from their basic salary, respectively. Every time the salary adjustment is announced, the pension annuity for all pensioners is adjusted to the same rate as in salary adjustment.

Due to Malaysia's public pension system whereby the percentage of pension annuity is depended on the amendment of maximum duration of service as well as the existence of derivative pension, in this study, the demographic risk is defined as the risk that the public workers is attaining the maximum duration of services at compulsory retirement age and the pensioners (or pension recipients) will live longer. Also, the salary risk is focusing on the increment of salary when the basic salary is adjusted.

TABLE I
 PERSONNEL ACCORDING TO GROUP OF SERVICE AND SALARY ADJUSTMENT RATE

Group of Service	Salary Adjustment Rate		
	2000 and 2002	2003	2007
Top Management	10%	RM110	7.5%
Management & Professional	10%	RM65	15%
Supporting I	10%	RM15	25%
Supporting II	10%	RM15	35%

IV. DYNAMICS HYPOTHESIS

In this research, an interview session was arranged with the Departmental Head of Actuary in Ministry of Finance to investigate the factors that affect pension expenditure and how they are interrelated. The next interview session was carried out with the Director of Pensions Division in Malaysia Public Service Department (PSD) in order to gain in depth information regarding the pension system for public workers. After that, few visits were conducted with the senior officers in pension division and deputy accountant of PSD to further discuss the pension system, available data and related

information. Through the literature review in [4]-[9], and from the interview sessions, causal loop diagram is used to analyze the inter-relationships among these factors.

Causal loop diagram (also known as feedback loop) is a part of system dynamic modeling which is used to analyze complex relationship that exists in dynamic system. A causal loop is referred to as influence diagram or mathematically known as directed graphs. A causal loop enlighten a dynamic process of a system in which the chain effects of a cause are traced, through a set of related variables, back to the original cause. A causal loop is formed when a set of variables has been linked together in a connected path. There are two types of causal loop which are Reinforcing loop (indicate by the symbol R+) and Balancing loop (indicate by the symbol B-). Balancing loops tend to stabilize the model and reinforcing loops tend to destabilize. The loop is defined as positive (known as reinforcing loop) when the number of negative relationships is even, otherwise the loop is negative (known as balancing loop). Causal loop also represent by an arrow headed line with a symbol "+" mean a change in the influencing variable will produce a change of the same direction in the target variable while the symbol "-" mean the effect will in a opposite direction between the influencing variable and the target variable. The causal loops relation is a helpful tool to predict the impact of desired factors in the system holistically [10].

Causal loop diagram of pension expenditure system consists of two parts – 1) causal loop diagram of population model and 2) causal loop diagram of pension expenditure. The first part of causal loop diagram illustrates three balancing loops and one reinforcing loop. In causal loop diagram of population model (fig. 2), appointment rate and numbers of new workers will increase the number of public workers (Reinforcing loop, R1). As mentioned, public workers consist of three groups of services which are top management workers, management & professional workers and supporting workers. Hence, any changes to the number of workers in group of service, retired workers from each group of service, total retired workers, and maturity rate will also cause an opposite changes to the number of public workers (Balancing loop, B1 and B2). Maturity rate and maturity level which represents the ratio of workers that reach compulsory retirement age will cause a decline to the numbers of public workers (Balancing loop, B3). Simultaneously, the number of retired workers from each group of service varies as a result of retirement rate and cessation rate.

The second part of causal loop analysis is on how the pension expenditure is estimated (fig. 3). Classification of retired worker is split up by a salary cohort also known as scheme of service. The total last basic salary for all salary cohorts is depended on total salary in each salary cohort while the total salary in each salary cohort is depended on numbers of retired workers in each salary cohort and the last basic salary in each salary cohort. Loop R1 represents the increment of last basic salary in each salary cohort as a result of salary adjustment. While, loop

B1 acts to decreases the total last basic salary for all salary cohorts as the expected pension expenditure increases. Also, the expected pension expenditure is determined by a total last basic salary for all salary cohorts and accrual rate. Accrual rate is defined as the percentage of pension annuity from employees' last basic salary. In the same time, last basic salary in each salary cohort will be affected by salary adjustment and adjustment rate while pension expenditure is affected by pension adjustment, adjustment rate and benefit cessation rate.

Fig. 2 Causal loop diagram of population model

Fig. 3 Causal loop diagram of pension expenditure

V.DEVELOPMENT OF SYSTEM DYNAMICS MODEL

In this research, all factors presented in fig. 2 and 3 were transformed into stock and flow diagrams (fig. 4-6) by using iThink software to build the system dynamics model of pension expenditure. The development of system dynamics model includes several types of variables such as stocks, flows, converters and connectors. Stock which is also known as levels act as a reservoir to accumulate quantities (represented by rectangle) and describe the condition of the system. The flows increasing (inflow) and decreasing (outflow) a stock are also known as rates (represented by valve). The condition of stock will depend on the rates while the rates can be affected by a factor affecting inflow or outflow which is known as converter or auxiliaries (represented by circle). Finally, the connectors represent cause and effect links within the model structure is represented by

the single-line arrow [3]. The system dynamics model of pension expenditure contains 3 main sectors which are the population sector, salary scheme sector and pension expenditure sector.

A. The Population Sector

Fig. 4: System dynamics model for population sector

The population sector illustrates the dynamics that are involved in various population categories. The number of public workers is depended on an appointment rate and the numbers of new workers. The public workers consist of top management group, management and professional group and supporting group. Therefore, there are three main stocks representing retired workers for each group of service. The total number of retired workers is from each of this group is then will affect maturity rate. Maturity rate represents the ratio of workers that reach compulsory retirement age and become pensioners. Also, due the existence of derivative pension, the cessation workers in each group of service represent number of pensioners that is no longer received pension annuity. The equations of this sector are (**S** = Stock, **R** = Rate, **C** = Converter):

$$\mathbf{S} \quad P(t) = P(t - dt) + M * dt \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{R} \quad M = MR * PW \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{C} \quad MR = \sum R_{T,P,S} / PW \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{S} \quad PW(t) = PW(t - dt) + (NW - M) * dt \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{R} \quad NW = PW * AR \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{S} \quad RW_{T,P,S}(t) =$$

$$RW_{T,P,S}(t - dt) + (R_{T,P,S} - CW_{T,P,S}) * dt \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{R} \quad R_{T,P,S} = RR_{T,P,S} * W_{T,P,S} \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{C} \quad W_{T,P,S} = PW * F_{T,P,S} \quad (8)$$

where P = pensioners, M = maturity, MR = maturity rate, PW = public workers, NW = new workers, AR = appointment rate, $RW_{T,P,S}$ = retired workers in top management, management & professional and supporting group, $R_{T,P,S}$ = retirement in top management, management & professional and supporting group,

$W_{T,P,S}$ = workers in top management, management & professional and supporting group, $F_{T,P,S}$ = fraction of workers in top management, management & professional and supporting group.

B. The Salary Scheme Sector

Fig. 5: System dynamics model for salary scheme sector

Salary scheme sector shows the retirement in top management group (similar procedures applies to management & professional and supporting group) which is categorized by salary cohort also known as scheme of services. Retirement in top management group depended on workers in top management group and top management retirement rate. In top management group, there are 7 salary schemes ranging from V1 until V7. The numbers of retired workers in each salary schemes is depended on retirement in top management group and retirement rate. Then, total salary in each salary scheme is influenced by the number of retired workers and the last basic salary in each salary scheme. The last basic salary in each salary scheme is affected by two types of adjustment rate which are based on percentage and non-percentage. Lastly, total salary for all salary schemes determines the last basic salary rate and total last basic salary for top management group. The equations of this sector are (**S** = Stock, **R** = Rate, **C** = Converter):

$$\mathbf{R} \quad R_T = W_T * RR_T \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{C} \quad RW_{V1-V7} = R_T * RR_{V1-V7} \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{C} \quad TS_{V1-V7} = LBS_{V1-V7} * RW_{V1-V7} \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{S} \quad LBS_{V1-V7}(t) =$$

$$LBS_{V1-V7}(t - dt) + (SA_{V1-V7}) * dt \quad (12)$$

$$C \ SA_{V1-V7} = (LBS_{V1-V7} * ADRP) + ADRNP \quad (13)$$

$$S \ TLBS_T(t) = TLBS_T(t-dt) + LBSR \quad (14)$$

$$R \ LBSR = \sum TS_{V1-V7} \quad (15)$$

where R_T = retirement in top management group, W_T = workers in top management group, RR_T = retirement rate of top management group, TS_{V1-V7} = total salary in scheme V1-V7, LBS_{V1-V7} = last basic salary in scheme V1-V7, RW_{V1-V7} = retired workers in scheme V1-V7, SA_{V1-V7} = salary adjustment in scheme V1-V7, $ADRP$ = adjustment rate based on percentage, $ADRNP$ = adjustment rate based on non percentage, $TLBS_T$ = total last basic salary in top management group, $LBSR$ = last basic salary rate.

C. Pension Expenditure Sector

Fig. 6: System dynamics model for pension expenditure sector

The pension expenditure sector is the focus of this study because it is the main interest of the proposed model and related to all other sectors. In pension expenditure sector, the pension expenditure is calculated for top management group (similar procedures applies to management and professional and supporting group) by referring to the principles used in [8] and [9]. From the total last basic salary in top management group, the expected pension expenditure is determined by the total last basic salary and accrual rate. The calculation of pension expenditure includes pension adjustment too. It means when the salary adjustment is announced, the pension annuity for all pensioners is adjusted to the same rate as in salary adjustment. The pension adjustment consists of two types of adjustment rate which are based on percentage and non-percentage. Pension adjustment based on percentage adjustment rate is influenced by the pension expenditure and the percentage of adjustment rate. While, pension adjustment based on non-percentage adjustment rate is determined by the total numbers of pensioners and the non-percentage adjustment rate, RM 110. Simultaneously, pension expenditure is affected by benefit cessation rate. The equations of this sector are (S = Stock, R = Rate, C = Converter):

$$S \ PE_T(t) = PE_T(t-dt) + (EPE + PA - BC) * dt \quad (16)$$

$$R \ EPE = TLBS_T * ACR \quad (17)$$

$$R \ PA = (PE * ADRP) + TANP \quad (18)$$

$$C \ TANP = RW_T * ADRNP \quad (19)$$

where PE_T = pension expenditure for top management group, EPE = expected pension expenditure, PA = pension adjustment, BC = benefit cessation, $TLBS_T$ = total last basic salary for top management group, ACR = accrual rate, $TANP$ = total adjustment based on non percentage, $ADRP$ = adjustment rate based on percentage, $ADRNP$ = adjustment rate based on non percentage.

Pension expenditure for management & professional group and supporting I & II group is calculated as similar procedures applies to top management group. In management & professional group, the salary schemes are ranging from scheme 41 until scheme 54 while in supporting group, the salary schemes are ranging from scheme 1 until scheme 16 for supporting II group and scheme 17 until scheme 40 for supporting I group.

VI. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

An actual data provided by Public Service Department is used to simulate the system dynamics model of pension expenditure from 1995 to 2027. The time step for simulation is 1 year and information of the model base-run is listed in table II.

TABLE II
 INFORMATION OF THE MODEL BASE RUN

Parameter	Value
Appointment rate	0.03
Retirement rate in top management group	0.01
Retirement rate in management & professional group	0.004
Retirement rate in supporting group	0.01
Fraction of top management group	0.01
Fraction of management & professional group	0.22
Fraction of supporting group	0.77
Range of retirement rate for each salary scheme in top management group	0.002 - 0.6
Range of retirement rate for each salary scheme in management & professional group	0.0001-0.5
Range of retirement rate for each salary scheme in supporting group	0.0001-0.2

In the base-run simulation, we assume the initial value of accrual rate is 0.5. This rate implies that all workers have been in service for 25 years and eligible to received 50% pension annuity from their last basic salary. We also assume starting 2008, the pension annuity will be paid continuously to the eligible family member if the pensionable officer died. The base-run simulation results of pension expenditure for top management group, management & professional group and supporting I & supporting II group were presented in fig. 7.

Along with the time, it is shown that pension expenditure for all group of service increased. The effect of salary adjustment can be seen clearly after 2008 which pension expenditure is continuously increased for each service group.

Fig. 7: Simulation result of pension expenditure for all group of service

Next, two different scenarios were simulated to examine whether the simulation model perform correctly when some parameters value were changed. In each scenario, different shocks on certain parameters were imposed, and the effect on total pension expenditure (total pension expenditure is the summation of pension expenditure for all group of service) was analyzed by comparing the result with the base-run scenario. In this simulation, salary adjustment rate, appointment rate and retirement rate were chosen as a testing parameter since these factors have significant influence on pension expenditure.

Scenario I

In the first scenario, the parameters involves were salary adjustment rate, appointment rate and retirement rate. There were two types of salary adjustment rate – 1) adjustment rate based on percentage and 2) adjustment rate based on non-percentage. According to policy in Malaysia’s pension system, depending on government’s financial capability, for every period of 5 years the basic salary will be adjusted. From this policy, three salary adjustment – in 2013, 2018, and 2023, will be apply in this scenario. We assumed the salary adjustment rate will follow the same rate as in the historical data (table III). Then, the value of appointment rate and retirement rate for each group of service remains the same as in the base-run simulation.

TABLE III

ASSUMPTIONS ON FUTURE SALARY ADJUSTMENT RATE

Group of Service	Salary Adjustment Rate		
	2013	2018	2023
Top Management	10%	RM110	7.5%
Management & Professional	10%	RM65	15%
Supporting I	10%	RM15	25%
Supporting II	10%	RM15	35%

Fig. 8 displayed the result of salary adjustment in 2013, 2018

and 2023. It shows that the graph of base-run scenario and salary adjustment shock scenario increased along time. Also, it is observed that the graph with salary adjustment scenario show a significant increase in 2023 when there is relatively higher salary adjustment shock in the simulation model. It is indicate that the system has successfully captured the salary adjustment shocks.

Fig. 8: Simulation result of total pension expenditure with salary adjustment shock.

Scenario II

In scenario II, the parameters involves were the same as Scenario I with an introduction of shock on appointment rate and retirement rate starting from 2009 until 2027. We assumed the value of appointment rate and retirement rate double from the original values in the base-run simulation – appointment rate increased to 0.06 and retirement rate for top management, management & professional group and supporting group increased to 0.02, 0.008 and 0.02, respectively. Meanwhile, value of salary adjustment rate will remain the same as in Scenario I. Fig. 9 depicted the result of total pension expenditure with a shock imposed on salary adjustment, appointment rate and retirement rate. The increment of appointment rate and retirement rate values causes higher pension expenditure. It is because more workers were retired and thus policymakers have to pay more pension annuity. Therefore, the simulation model shown significant changes when a shock on salary adjustment rate, appointment rate and retirement rate are simultaneously imposed. There was a significant increment of pension expenditure when a higher value of salary adjustment rate (particularly in 2023), appointment rate and retirement rate imposed in the simulation. Therefore, it is proved that the design of system dynamics model of pension expenditure model is acceptable/reasonable and the model can reflect different impact on pension expenditure due to demographic and salary changes.

Fig. 9: Simulation result of total pension expenditure with salary adjustment, appointment rate and retirement rate shock.

it can be concluded that demographic and salary changes will continuously affect pension expenditure.

VII. APPLICATION OF THE MODEL

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Based on developed system dynamics model, a management flight simulator was constructed. Management flight simulator is a user's interface that acts as a decision making tool for policymaker to simulate interactive experimentation of policy changes. The user interface of the management flight simulator is shown in fig. 10. There were two main components with total of five control panels in the management flight simulator – 1) accrual rate adjustment and 2) salary adjustment rate. Any changes in policy made by policymaker can be simulated by adjustments to these parameters in management flight simulator. Results from these changes were displayed in two forms – graph pad and numerical display at middle of simulator.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Disney, R. and Johnson, P., *Pension systems & retirement incomes across OECD countries*, Edward Elgar, 2001, pp. 1-3.
- [2] Chang, K.W., "A risk management perspective on public pension reform," PhD diss., Boston University, 2000.
- [3] Maani, K.E & Cavana, R.Y. *Systems Thinking and Modeling, Understanding Change and Complexity*, Pearson Education N.Z press, 2000, pp. 16-70.
- [4] Chang, S.C., "Optimal pension funding through dynamic simulation: the case of Taiwan public employees retirement system," *Insurance, Mathematics & Economics*, vol. 24, pp. 187-199,1999.
- [5] Chang, S.C and Cheng, Y.H., "Pension valuation under uncertainties: implementation of a stochastic & dynamic monitoring system," *The Journal of Risk & Insurance*, vol. 69, pp. 171- 192, 2002.
- [6] Chaim, R. M., "Combining ALM and System Dynamics in Pension Funds," in *online Proc. of the 24th International Refereed Conference of System Dynamics Society*, Netherlands, 2006.
- [7] Chaim, R. M., "Dynamic stochasticity in the control of liquidity in asset and liability management (ALM) for pension funds," in *online Proc. of the 25th International Refereed Conference of System Dynamics Society*, Boston,2007.
- [8] Jimeno, J.F., Rojas, J.A. and Puente, S., "Modelling the impact of aging on social security expenditures," *Economic Modelling*, vol. 25, 2008, pp. 201-224.
- [9] Shimada, T, Kameyama, S, Uchino, A, Machida, K and Watanabe, M, "Simulation model of Japanese welfare annuity system," in *online Proc. of the 8th International Refereed Conference of System Dynamics Society*, Chestnut Hill, USA, 1990.
- [10] Chaim, R. and Streit, R.E. "Pension funds governance: combining SD, Agent based modeling and fuzzy logic to address Dynamic Asset and Liability Management (ALM) problem," in *online Proc. of the 26th International Refereed Conference of System Dynamics*, Society, Athens, 2008.

Fig. 10: The interface of management flight simulator

We simulate the effect on pension expenditure with accrual rate increased to 0.6 using the management flight simulator. The increment of accrual rate to 0.6 means policymaker has to pay 60% pension annuity from workers' last basic salary and we assumed the pension annuity will continuously paid until the pensioners (or pension recipients) died. The result of the simulation in 2027 is particularly shown in table IV.

TABLE IV
SIMULATION RESULT OF PENSION EXPENDITURE IN 2027
Pension Expenditure in 2027 (in Ringgit Malaysia)

Top Management	Management & Professional	Supporting I	Supporting II
36,446,689.23	143,339,998.42	432,444,383.82	200,573,870.30

From the simulation result, with an accrual rate of 0.6, pension expenditure in 2027 for top management, management & professional, supporting I and supporting II group reaches approximately RM36,446,689.23, RM143,339,998.42, RM432,444,383.82 and RM200,573,870.30 respectively. It is shown that pension expenditure in each group of service in 2027 increases 100% from pension expenditure in 1995. Higher pension expenditure was affected due to increment of accrual rate and higher life expectancies of pensioners (or pension recipients) which imply policy maker have to pay pension annuity for a longer time. Based on the simulation conducted,